
University St. Kliment Ohridski Bitola
Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality Ohrid

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES
XVII International Scientific Conference on Services Sector
INSCOSES, Ohrid, 26-27 September 2024

CIP - Каталогизација во публикација
Национална и универзитетска библиотека "Св. Климент Охридски",
Скопје

338.48(062)

33(062)

338.47(062)

640.4(062)

INTERNATIONAL Scientific Conference on Service sector INSCOSES (17 ;
2024 ; Ohrid)

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES ; XVII International Scientific
Conference on Service sector INSCOSES, Ohrid, 26-27 September 2024
[Електронски извор] / [organizing committee Aleksandar Trajkov ... и
др.]. - Текст во PDF формат, содржи 435 стр., илустр. - Ohrid : Faculty
of tourism and hospitality, 2025

Начин на пристапување (URL): <https://zenodo.org/communities/inscoses/>
(Слободен пристап). - Наслов преземен од екранот. - Опис на изворот на
ден 26.02.2025. - Библиографија кон трудовите

ISBN 978-608-4676-41-6

а) Туризам -- Собири б) Гастрономија -- Собири в) Економија -- Собири г)
Царина -- Собири

COBISS.MK-ID 65372677

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES
XVII International Scientific Conference on Services Sector INSCOSES, Ohrid,
26-27 September 2024
ISBN 978-608-4676-41-6

UDK 640.43-048.58:004.773.6/.7(497.11)
640.43-048.58:004.738.5(497.11)
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14979491

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS AND INFLUENCERS ON RESTAURANT CHOICE OF GENERATION Z

Goran Perić

Toplica Academy of Applied Studies, Department of Business School Blace, Blace
goran.peric@vpskp.edu.rs

Sandra Dramićanin

University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Hotel Management and Tourism, Vrnjačka
Banja
sandradramicanin@hotmail.com

Marko Gašić

Toplica Academy of Applied Studies, Department of Business School Blace, Blace
gasicmarko@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

We have witnessed that social networks play a big role in modern society and influence their users. Through social networks, potential users research past experiences and ratings and thus make decisions about using certain products or services. This paperwork investigates how social media and influences impact the decision of potential guests to visit a restaurant. First of all, this paper identifies the way users use social networks. It then compares different types of social networks and their impact on users. In the third part, this paper analyzes the impact of influences on the restaurant choice. This study included 148 respondents belonging to Generation Z from the Republic of Serbia. The measurement techniques used are descriptive statistics and t-tests. The results of this research show that social networks and influencers have a positive influence on the restaurant choice by respondents in Generation Z, with the fact that there is a more significant impact of influences. Among the three factors with the greatest impact are: the way the influencers present the restaurant, an exciting approach to the food, and the presentation of a restaurants ambience. As for the most influential social networks, they are TikTok and Instagram.

KEY WORDS: social network, influencers, restaurant choice, Gen Z

INTRODUCTION

Marketing represents one of the powerful tools for influencing the behavior of potential and loyal users and decision-making (Veljković & Đorđević, 2010). Marketing professionals use psychological theories, and social media, personalize products and services to bring them closer to potential users, and use creativity to persuade consumers to buy a product or service. Marketing professionals realized communication with potential consumers, connecting with people on all continents, and building a loyal potential user are the easiest and fastest through social networks (Gardašević et al., 2018).

Currently, social media and social networks have a significant impact on the decision-making process when purchasing or using a product or service (Bronner & de Hoog, 2014). Social networks influence purchase decisions by shaping the behavior of potential customers and providing information about the services or products that the potential customer will purchase (Russo & Simeona, 2017). Through social media, people are permitted to share their opinions related to the product or service used, by expressing their satisfaction or dissatisfaction. The impressions, ratings, and comments left in this way can influence the choice of a potential customer whether to make a purchase decision or not (Liu & Lopez, 2016). People's decisions to purchase a product or service are heavily influenced by recommendations, ratings, reviews, and content generated by other people (Boon-Long & Wongsurawat, 2015). The large amount of information available on social networks is useful for potential consumers to learn about the experiences of others and to make a purchase decision.

Social networks have become an inseparable part of modern culture and influence restaurant trends. They represent an excellent tool through which restaurants can increase visibility about the competition and raise the awareness of potential guests about the existence of their brand (Lepkowska-White et al., 2019). Through social networks and content shared by the restaurant's marketing team, guests, and influencers, it is possible to reach interesting content and influential marketing, so restaurants can reach a larger number of potential guests and leave an impression on them, and to create a desire to visit the restaurant (Mhlanga & Tichaawa, 2017). To develop a positive impression among potential customers, restaurants must foster brand loyalty and use social networking platforms to increase their presence in the

online world (Wantah & Mandagi, 2024). Partnering with influential influencers can help them reach more users as soon as possible, especially from Generation Z, because influencers have the power to influence the purchasing decisions of those who follow them (Leung et al., 2022; Azim & Nair, 2021).

One of the significant impacts achieved by social media influencers is to drive sales through service and product recommendations and encourage potential users to purchase a specific product and service (Bushara et al., 2023; Lim et al., 2017). Influencers can stimulate the decisions of potential users through authentic recommendations, comments, and product ratings (Leung et al., 2022). If potential customers are confident in the influencer's recommendation, they are more likely to purchase the product or service (Lou et al., 2022).

Generation Z represents a large population that influences the restaurant sector, so it is necessary to adapt to their wishes and needs. They are used to influencers posting their ratings, comments, and pictures of restaurant food, and modern businesses rely more and more on influencers and their influence on consumers. Therefore, restaurants are in a situation where they need influencers to visit the restaurant and give ratings about satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the taste of the food, its smell and appearance, the ambiance of the restaurant, service, and so more (AlQuadi et al., 2020).

The daily use of social networks has prompted research into how influencers and their content influence restaurant choices. There is very little research in the world that has examined the impact of influencers on the decision of potential guests to visit a certain restaurant. Most of the research is focused on the overall influence of social media or social networks, but there is not a large number of research that specifically investigated the impact of influencers on the decision to visit a particular restaurant. There are also studies on the influence of social networks on Generation Z when to choose a restaurant, but they have not been conducted in the Republic of Serbia. Well, this paper has both a theoretical and a practical contribution of influencers impact on the restaurant choice of Generation Z.

LITERATURE REVIEW THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Social networks give people the ability to connect with friends, family, and people with the same interests, even in remote places around the planet. Social networks are available everywhere, have a global reach, and contain an enormous amount of information (Dramićanin et al., 2023). Connections through social networks help people maintain relationships, share interests, and create a sense of belonging, respect, and support. Nowadays, social networks are known for sparking conversation and allowing people to participate in discussions, learn and develop. News spreads rapidly on social networks, so it keeps users up to date with daily events. This represents an extraordinary advantage compared to other information channels.

Also, social networks help businesses find and maintain contact with users of products and services (Mack et al., 2017). By showing the positive features of products and services and how to use them, companies can attract people's attention and build trust through social media content (Infante & Mardikaningsih, 2022). The possibilities of social networks are unlimited, they can help companies market products and services and turn potential clients into satisfied and loyal users (Oncioiu et al., 2021).

In the modern age, social networks have become an important instrument by which users' conceptions, feelings, and experiences are shaped (Luo & Zhong, 2015). Different social networks have different effects on users, and modern behavior created through interaction with other people has an impact on everyday shopping. Research shows that social networks have a positive influence on the restaurant choice by users (Rahman, 2023; Yang, 2017; Park & Nikolau, 2015; Zhang et al., 2010). After collecting information, potential users of restaurant services evaluate their options based on important criteria such as food quality, price, ambiance, service, location and choose a restaurant to visit and enjoy a meal (Radujković, 2021). Research has shown that the factors that most influence the restaurant choice by potential users are online reviews and reviews from social networks (Rahman et al., 2023). Nowadays, restaurant users choose where to dine based on the diverse alternatives they find on social networks (Guvenc et al., 2023). The largest number of users prefer restaurants whose previous users have left their own experiences and ratings, then those whose guests have not. Social networks can be a crucial guide when choosing a restaurant.

This paper aims to determine whether factors (social networks and influencers) influence the restaurant choice, which social network has the greatest influence, and in what way influencers impact the restaurant choice as far as their roots are concerned.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Some studies dealt with the influence of social networks and influencers on the restaurant choice (Dinc, 2023; Rahman, 2023; Yaris & Aykol, 2022; Hwang et al., 2021; Ramos et al., 2021; Siddiqui, 2020; Yang, 2017; Park & Nikolau, 2015; Zhang et al., 2010). Relying on the previous experiences of users of restaurant services regarding the ambiance, cleanliness, quality of service, taste of food, and dedication of employees, potential users can decide to visit the restaurant (Cakici & Cakul, 2022; Radujković, 2021).

Figure 1. Research model

Generation Z searches for information on food quality, restaurant appearance, and hygiene on social networks, and based on that decides which restaurant to visit (Hoang et al., 2024). The more positive the image customers have of a restaurant and share it on social networks, the more likely Generation Z people are to visit it (Shah et al., 2023). Based on the above, the following hypothesis is put forward:

H₁: Social networks influence the restaurant choice of Generation Z.

Social networks deeply shape the worldview of Generation Z. Social networks thus shape their self-image, relationships, and perception of the world, but also help in decision-making (Waworuntu et al., 2022). Not all social networks have the same impact on users. What may affect one type of user will not affect another type. A generational gap is especially noticeable in the use of

certain social networks, so their impact on users is not the same (Hwang et al. 2021, O’Keeffe et al., 2011).

Figure 2. Most frequently used social networks of Generation Z and Internet users worldwide

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1446950/gen-z-internet-users-social-media-use/> , retrieved: 25.07.2024.

Social networking platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, Facebook, and X are popular among Generation Z and are used as places to gather information about restaurants (Tan, 2023; Altun et al., 2022; Hanifawati et al., 2019). Generation Z follows influencers' content and their work on content that goes beyond a single network presence, giving them the ability to influence across multiple social media platforms (Wielki, 2020). Based on previous studies on the use of social networks and their influence on Generation Z in terms of purchasing choices (Dwiandini, 2024; Putri, 2024; Plotez et al., 2023; Dirir, 2022), the following hypotheses are put forward:

H₂: The social network TikTok has a greater influence on Generation Z when choosing a restaurant than the social network Facebook.

H₃: Social network Instagram has a greater influence on Generation Z when choosing a restaurant than social network X.

Unlike members of older generations who rely on online reviews, members of Generation Z lean towards influential content creators (influencers) (Tanwar et al., 2022). Generation Z trusts influencers because their content makes people feel like they are following a friend and their advice (Hazari & Sethna,

2023). When an influencer recommends something, Generation Z takes it as a recommendation from a friend, not a paid advertisement. So, when presenting a restaurant on social networks, members of Generation Z do not perceive that the influencer is advertising something to them, but rather that, as a friend, they recommend the food in the restaurant, the ambiance, the location and the like (Song et al., 2024; Philip et al., 2024; Pervin & Kahn, 2024). Based on that, the following hypothesis is put forward:

H₄: Influencers with their content on social networks influence the restaurant choice of Generation Z.

Social network users enthusiastically search social networks to find out what other users have said about a particular product or service (Stanojević et al., 2024). Influencer marketing makes it possible to reach an audience of potential users of restaurant services who trust what their favorite people (influencers) recommend (Pervin & Khan, 2024). The results of previous research show that each step when deciding on choosing a restaurant is positively correlated with trust in the influencer and the credibility of what he represents on the social network related to a specific restaurant (Pervin & Kan, 2024; Dinc, 2023). The lifestyles created by influencers are what their followers want to emulate (Andreani et al., 2021). In this way, influencers enable others to live through them and to convey the experience experienced in the restaurant closer to them, thus evoking the desire to visit (Philip et al., 2024). Based on the above, the following hypothesis is put forward:

H₅: The content of influencers has a greater influence on the restaurant choice, than content on social networks published by other users, who are not influencers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY RESEARCH DESIGN

The research aims to examine how social networks and influencers impact the restaurant choice to Generation Z. To conduct the research, a questionnaire was used, which was constructed based on two questionnaires used by researchers Philip et al. (2024) and Pauliene & Sedneva (2019) in their research. The questions were translated in the spirit of the Serbian language and then distributed to the respondents.

DATA COLLECTION

The primary and secondary data were used for this research. Secondary data were collected based on electronic databases that contain works on this topic. Primary data was collected based on the distribution of a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed online. Respondents had to be from the territory of the Republic of Serbia and belong to Generation Z, use social networks, and have visited a restaurant in the last 6 months.

The questionnaire consists of three parts. In the first part, respondents answered questions related to the use of social networks, in the second part they ranked social networks according to the influence it has on them, and in the third part they gave answers related to the impact of influencer content on social networks related to restaurants. For giving answers in the first and third parts, a Likert scale was used, where respondents selected answers according to their views: 1 - absolutely disagree; 2 - disagree; 3 - neither agree nor disagree; 4- agree; 5 - absolutely agree. While answering the second part, they were supposed to rank social networks on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 represents the least impact and 5 the greatest impact that the social network has on the respondents.

In this research, the independent variable is represented by social networks, influencers, and the content that they share on social networks, while the dependent variable is the restaurant choice.

For the analysis of the postulate model, it is necessary to measure the reliability factor. Hypotheses were tested using SPSS 21 software. The results will be presented in two parts: data reliability and descriptive statistics and t-test.

Table 1. Cronbach Alpha for the social networks use in a restaurant choosing

Item	Cronbach Alpha	Std. Alpha
U1	0.8734	0.8727
U2	0.8825	0.8799
U3	0.8772	0.8750
U4	0.8902	0.8892
U5	0.8866	0.8851
U6	0.8857	0.8838

Source: Author's calculation

A general rule is that a Cronbach Alpha of 0.7 or higher is considered acceptable for group comparisons, while a Cronbach Alpha of 0.8 or higher is desirable for individual comparisons. All Cronbach Alpha values for the social networks use in a restaurant choosing are considered acceptable.

Table 2. Cronbach Alpha for the social network degree of influence

Item	Cronbach Alpha	Std. Alpha
SM1	0.8982	0.8962
SM2	0.8838	0.8827
SM3	0.8754	0.8753
SM4	0.8899	0.8880
SM5	0.8973	0.8974

Source: Author's calculation

All Cronbach Alpha values for the social network degree of influence are considered acceptable.

Table 3. Cronbach Alpha of the influencer content impact on the restaurant choice

Item	Cronbach Alpha	Std. Alpha
I1	0.8717	0.8717
I2	0.8826	0.8804
I3	0.8792	0.8772
I4	0.8815	0.8794
I5	0.8803	0.8784
I6	0.8801	0.8774
I7	0.8799	0.8772

Source: Author's calculation

All the Cronbach Alpha values of the influencer content impact on the restaurant choice are considered acceptable.

Table 4. Cronbach Alpha for all statements

Item	Cronbach Alpha	Std. Alpha
All items	0.8892	0.8876

Source: Author's calculation

With a value of 0.8892, the reliability factor is considered acceptable for all statements.

RESULTS

The first part of the questionnaire contains questions related to the social networks use by respondents, to examine their behaviors related to social networks. The respondents gave the following answers shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Use of social networks in restaurant choice

Item	Mean	SD
U1	3.59	1.2118
U2	3.34	0.8861
U3	3.47	1.0329
U4	3.66	0.9163
U5	3.45	0.9131
U6	3.21	1.0051

Source: Author's calculation

The results show that the respondents use social networks to find information about restaurants, where they value the ratings of real guests more than the ratings on social networks, which they still consider important when choosing a restaurant. The majority of respondents consider that the information they receive on social networks is important, and to be sure of their restaurant choice, they read ratings and comments.

The second part of the questionnaire investigated the degree of social networks influences in a restaurant choosing.

Table 6. Degree of social network influence

Item	Mean	SD
SM1	2.65	1.1715
SM2	4.14	1.1044
SM3	3.62	1.3653
SM4	2.43	1.1900
SM5	1.82	0.9698

Source: Author's calculation

The results show that the greatest influence degree on the decision to visit a restaurant among Generation Z has Instagram, then TikTok, followed by Facebook, then X (Twitter), and then YouTube.

In the third part of the research, it was investigated the impact of influencers and their content on social networks on the restaurant choice of Generation Z.

Table 7. The impact of influencers in a restaurant choosing

Item	Mean	SD
I1	3.40	1.2657
I2	3.41	0.9955
I3	3.35	1.0996
I4	3.36	0.9976
I5	3.26	1.0825
I6	3.36	0.9548
I7	3.36	0.9760

Source: Author's calculation

The results show that an exciting approach to restaurant food presentation by influencers is important to Generation Z. As well as the way the influencers present the restaurant, they also think that the influencers presentation of the ambiance is important. At the same time, they think that influencer ratings and recommendations can encourage them to visit a restaurant, but they don't always look for it when choosing a restaurant.

To compare the differences in the levels of impact of social networks and influencers on the restaurant choice of Generation Z, a t-test was used. The results are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. T-test

	p	t	df	St. Dev error	N	Mean	SD
Social media	0.0001	16.3810	294	0.370	148	20.71	4.09
Influencers	0.0001	18.1845	294	0.486	148	23.49	5.61

Source: Author's calculation

The two-tailed p-value is less than 0.0001. By conventional criteria, this difference is considered extremely statistically significant. The values show that there is a difference in impact, and that influencers have more impact than social networks on the restaurant choice of Generation Z.

DISCUSSION

This research dealt with the topic of the impact of social networks and influencers on the restaurant choice of Generation Z. To investigate the influence, a research model was set up and five hypotheses were formulated. Based on the research results, it is concluded that:

- H₁: Social networks influence the restaurants choice of Generation Z - proven. The results show that Generation Z, when choosing a restaurant, looks for information on social networks, and then they use it to decide which restaurant to visit.
- H₂: The social network TikTok has a greater influence on Generation Z when choosing a restaurant than the social network Facebook - proven. The results show that the social network TikTok has a greater influence on Generation Z compared to the social network Facebook when choosing a restaurant.
- H₃: The social network Instagram has a greater influence on Generation Z when it comes to choosing a restaurant than the social network X - proven. The results show that the social network Instagram has a greater influence on Generation Z compared to the social network X, when it comes to choosing a restaurant.
- H₄: With their content on social networks, influencers impact the restaurant choice of Generation Z - proven. The results show that based on the content they see on social networks, which are posted by influencers, members of Generation Z decide to choose a restaurant. The most common content based on which they make a decision is the restaurant presentation, the presentation of the food, and the ambiance.
- H₅: The content of influencers has a greater influence on choosing a restaurant than content on social networks published by other users, who are not influencers - proven. The results of the t-test indicate that there is a statistically significant difference in the impact of influencers and social networks on the restaurant choice of Generation Z, and it has been proven that there is a greater influence of influencers, than the content of other users on social networks when it comes to the restaurant choice.

The results obtained based on the testing of hypotheses H₁, H₂, H₃, H₄, and H₅ are in agreement with the results obtained from secondary data, based on available literature. In their research, Philip et al. (2024) proved that influencers effect members of Generation Z on restaurant choice and that social networks also have an influence on restaurant choice. A study by Ding

et al. (2022) and Pauline & Sedneva (2019) also observed a positive influence of social networks and influencers on the restaurant choice of Generation Z, as well as the research of Shah et al. (2023). In the research of Tan et al. (2023), Wiweka et al. (2023), Yaris & Aykol (2020), and Wachyuni (2023) YouTube as a social network was shown as a factor with a great influence on a restaurant choice. In this research, YouTube as a social network has the least degree of influence on the restaurant choice. This result is unusual and if you look at Figure 2, where YouTube as a social network is the most popular among Generation Z. Research conducted by researchers Donc (2023), Azim & Nair (2021), and Alqadi (2020), proves that the impact of influencers is greater, but the influence of other users from social networks, on the restaurant choice, which is in agreement with the results related to the hypothesis H₅ in this research.

The presented results have both practical and theoretical implications. The results can serve as inspiration for restaurant owners and managers to collaborate with influencers to adapt to the modern needs of Generation Z and keep up with marketing strategies in the market, in this way, in addition to creating loyal users and the brand. They also increase the average and profitability of the restaurant, which is also one of the basic goals of business.

The theoretical implications are reflected in the completion of both domestic and foreign literature. Since there are no paper works on this topic in domestic literature, this manuscript can serve as a starting point for other researchers. As far as foreign literature is concerned, given that the five hypotheses are in agreement with works from world research, they can also be used for comparative analysis between countries.

CONCLUSION

Modern society relies heavily on the use Internet and social networks. Every day, younger generations spend a lot of time searching Internet and social networks to find the necessary information. When purchasing products and services, the majority of the population belonging to Generation Z consults social networks and follows the profiles of influencers to find out what they think about it. It is necessary to pay attention to understanding the decision-making process of people belonging to Generation Z on restaurant choice. This paper included the most common factors such as social networks to see the impact of influencers on restaurant choice. The data collected by this research showed that social networks and influencers impact the decision-

making process to Generation Z. The results also revealed that the social networks TikTok and Instagram and the content shared on them have the greatest influence on consumers' decision to visit a particular restaurant. In addition, important factors that impact respondents to decide to visit a restaurant are the way influencers represent the entire restaurant, present the food, and show the restaurant's ambiance. Based on the results, restaurant owners are recommended to use influencers to present their restaurants on social networks and thus attract members of Generation Z to visit their restaurants, and enjoy the food, service, and ambiance.

This research has several limitations. The first limitation refers to the territorial distribution. The researchers did not have the opportunity to distribute the respondents equally across all regions in the Republic of Serbia, so the respondents are unevenly represented, which makes further research and comparisons within the region impossible.

Another limitation relates to the representation of only Generation Z, which does not fully represent the general population of users of restaurant services. So, the possibility of generalizing the results for the Republic of Serbia is limited and it is impossible to make a comparison with other countries for the entire population. A comparison is possible specifically for Generation Z.

Future research should include the population belonging to other generations, especially to determine the difference in the impact of social networks and influencers on the restaurant choice, among different generations. Then, future research could include more influencing factors and at the same time be concentrated exclusively on the content of the influencer, which would be divided by elements (display of food, display of restaurants, ambiance, preparation of food, service, etc.), and then the impact on the decision to visit the restaurant would be investigated. It is also possible to use alternative methods of analysis such as interviews and focus groups, for the easier understanding of the mutual relationship between influencers, their content on social networks, and the restaurant choice by potential service users.

REFERENCES:

AlQadi, R., Al-Nojaidi, H., Alabdulkareem, L., Alrazgan, M., Alghamdi, N., & Kamruzzaman, M. M. (2020, October). How social media influencers affect consumers' restaurant selection: statistical and sentiment analysis.

-
- In *2020 2nd International Conference on Computer and Information Sciences (ICCIS)* (pp. 1-6).
- Altun, Ö., Cizrelioğulları, M. N., & Babayiğit, M. V. (2022). The effects of social media on the food preferences of Generation Z within the scope of gastronomy tourism. In *Handbook on Tourism and Social Media* (pp. 412-425). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Andreani, F., Gunawan, L., & Haryono, S. (2021). Social media influencer, brand awareness, and purchase decision among Generation Z in Surabaya. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Kewirausahaan*, 23(1), 18-26.
- Azim, R., & Nair, P. B. (2021). Social media influencers and electronic word of mouth: the communication impact on restaurant patronizing. *Journal of Content, Community, and Communication*, 14(8), 46-56.
- Boon-Long, S., & Wongsurawat, W. (2015). Social media marketing evaluation using social network comments as an indicator for identifying consumer purchasing decision effectiveness. *Journal of Direct, Data and Digital Marketing Practice*, 17, 130-149.
- Bronner, F., & de Hoog, R. (2014). Social media and consumer choice. *International journal of market research*, 56(1), 51-71.
- Bushara, M. A., Abdou, A. H., Hassan, T. H., Sobaih, A. E. E., Albohnayh, A. S. M., Alshammari, W. G., ... & Elsaied, M. A. (2023). Power of social media marketing: how perceived value mediate the impact on restaurant followers' purchase intention, willingness to pay a premium price, and e-WoM? *Sustainability*, 15(6), 5331.
- Cakıcı, S., & Cankul, D. (2022). The Effect of Social Visibility on Restaurant Choice. *Journal of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*, 10(4), 3097-3122.
- Dinc, L. (2023). The influence of social media influencers on consumers' decision-making of restaurant choice. *Journal of Tourism Leisure and Hospitality*, 5(2), 115-124.
- Ding, L., Jiang, C., & Qu, H. (2022). Generation Z domestic food tourists experienced restaurant innovativeness toward destination cognitive food image and revisit intention. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 34(11), 4157-4177.
- Dirir, S. A. (2022). Investigating the impact of TikTok on Generation Z buying behavior and their insight into selecting brands. *Journal of the Market Research Society*, 1-9.
- Dramićanin, S., Perić, G., & Gašić, M. (2023, December). The impact of TikTok on travel decisions. In *International Scientific Conference on Economy, Management and Information Technologies*, 1(1), 129-138.

-
- Dwiandini, A. (2024). The use of social media influencers as a digital marketing strategy in Generation Z. *Journal of Humanities and Social Studies*, 8(1), 057-063.
- Gardašević, J., Ćirić, M., & Carić, M. (2018). Razumevanje motiva koršćenja društvenih mreža u funkciji unapređenja komunikacije sa potrošačima. *Marketing* 49(4), 311-324.
- Güvenç, N. Y., Köz, E. N., & Evren, S. (2023). Analysis of Customer Reviews on Korean Restaurant Experience: The Case of Zomato Istanbul. *Journal of Tourismology*, 9(1), 41-49.
- Hanifawati, T., Dewanti, V. W., & Saputri, G. D. (2019). The role of social media influencer on brand switching of millennial and gen Z: a study of food-beverage products. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 17(4), 625-638.
- Hazari, S., & Sethna, B. N. (2023). A comparison of lifestyle marketing and brand influencer advertising for Generation Z Instagram users. *Journal of Promotion Management*, 29(4), 491-534.
- Hoang, D. P., Nguyen Hai, D., Nguyen, V. T. N., Nong, H. T., Pham, P. T., & Tran, T. M. (2024). Factors affecting restaurant choices for traditional foods among Gen Y and Gen Z: a multigenerational study on Vietnamese “Pho”. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 7(2), 868-888.
- Hwang, J., Eves, A., & Stienmetz, J. L. (2021). The impact of social media use on consumers’ restaurant consumption experiences: A qualitative study. *Sustainability*, 13(12), 6581.
- Infante, A., & Mardikaningsih, R. (2022). The Potential of Social Media as a Means of Online Business Promotion. *Journal of Social Science Studies*, 2(2), 45-49.
- Lepkowska-White, E., Parsons, A., & Berg, W. (2019). Social media marketing management: an application to small restaurants in the US. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 13(3), 321-345.
- Leung, X. Y., Sun, J., & Asswailem, A. (2022). Attractive females versus trustworthy males: Explore gender effects in social media influencer marketing in Saudi restaurants. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 103, 103207.
- Lim, X. J., Radzol, A. M., Cheah, J., & Wong, M. W. (2017). The impact of social media influencers on purchase intention and the mediation effect of customer attitude. *Asian journal of business research*, 7(2), 19-36.
- Liu, Y., & Lopez, R. A. (2016). The impact of social media conversations on consumer brand choices. *Marketing Letters*, 27, 1-13.
- Lou, C., Chee, T., & Zhou, X. (2022). Reviewing the commercial and social impact of social media influencers. In *The dynamics of influencer marketing* (pp. 60-79). Routledge.

-
- Luo, Q., & Zhong, D. (2015). Using social network analysis to explain communication characteristics of travel-related electronic word-of-mouth on social networking sites. *Tourism management*, 46, 274-282.
- Mack, E. A., Marie-Pierre, L., & Redican, K. (2017). Entrepreneurs' use of internet and social media applications. *Telecommunications Policy*, 41(2), 120-139.
- Mhlanga, O., & Tichaawa, T. M. (2017). Influence of social media on customer experiences in restaurants: A South African study. *Tourism: An International Interdisciplinary Journal*, 65(1), 45-60.
- O'Keeffe, G. S., & Clarke-Pearson, K. (2011). The impact of social media on children, adolescents, and families. *Pediatrics*, 127(4), 800-804.
- Oncioiu, I., Căpușeanu, S., Topor, D. I., Tamaș, A. S., Solomon, A. G., & Dănescu, T. (2021). Fundamental power of social media interactions for building a brand and customer relations. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(5), 1702-1717.
- Park, S., & Nicolau, J. L. (2015). Asymmetric effects of online consumer reviews. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 50, 67-83.
- Pauliene, R., & Sedneva, K. (2019). The influence of recommendations in social media on purchase intentions of generations Y and Z. *Organizations and markets in emerging economies*, 10(2), 227-256.
- Pervin, M. T., & Khan, M. R. (2024). The Impact of Social Media Marketing on Consumers' Buying Decisions in the Restaurant Industry: Mediating Role of Trustworthiness. *Jindal Journal of Business Research*, 22786821241235741.
- Philip, A. M., Othman, Z., Talib, A. H., Saiful Bakhtiar, M. F., & Kedin, N. A. (2024). Social Media Influencer (SMI) restaurant reviews and students' patronization decision. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Culinary Arts*, 16(1), 682-696.
- Plotz, S., Martinez, L. M., Martinez, L. F., & Ramos, F. R. (2023). The influence of TikTok videos on German Gen Z consumers' attitude and purchase intention towards sustainable brands. In *Digital Marketing & eCommerce Conference* (pp. 270-289). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Putri, N., Prasetya, Y., Handayani, P. W., & Fitriani, H. (2024). TikTok Shop: How trust and privacy influence Generation Z's purchasing behaviors. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 10(1), 2292759.
- Radujković, I. (2021). Tripadvisor reviews vs. Instagram posts: Influence on Consumer restaurant choice from Viennese Perception. Model Vienna University.
- Rahman, M., Zahin, M., & Akter, S. (2023). Consumers' Restaurant Selection through Social Media Review. *The Comilla University Journal of Business Studies*, 8(1), 41-64.

-
- Ramos, K., Cuamea, O., Morgan, J., & Estrada, A. (2021). Social networks' factors driving consumer restaurant choice: An exploratory analysis. In *Advances in Artificial Intelligence, Software and Systems Engineering: Proceedings of the AHFE 2020 Virtual Conferences on Software and Systems Engineering, and Artificial Intelligence and Social Computing, July 16-20, 2020, USA* (pp. 158-164). Springer International Publishing.
- Russo, C., & Simeone, M. (2017). The growing influence of social and digital media: Impact on consumer choice and market equilibrium. *British Food Journal*, 119(8), 1766-1780.
- Shah, P., Bhusal, N., & Chettri, K. K. (2023). Influence of Social Media Usage on Generation Z's Choice in Selecting Restaurants in Kathmandu. *Journal of Business and Social Sciences Research*, 8(1), 95-110.
- Siddiqui, M. A. (2020). Effects of social media marketing and women on consumer choice decision related to the restaurant industry. *International Research Journal of Marketing & Economics*, 7(6), 1-8.
- Song, J., Qu, H., & Li, X. (2024). It takes a village!: Customer value co-creation behavior in restaurant social media-based brand community. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 48(2), 327-352.
- Stanojević, M., Kalenjuck, P. B., Šmugović, S., & Stošić, T. (2024). Social networks and their influence on the choice of restaurant in the example of the hospitality industry of the Republic of Serbia. *Turističko poslovanje*, (33), 79-91.
- Tan, J. Y., Chan, L. Y., Che Tan, S., Wong, E. Y., & Chaichi, K. (2023). Generating Competitiveness through Trending Marketing strategies, Case of Gen Z Consumers in the Restaurant industry. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 10(4), 471-496.
- Tanwar, A. S., Chaudhry, H., & Srivastava, M. K. (2022). Trends in influencer marketing: A review and bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 22(1), 1-27.
- Veljković, S., & Đorđević, A. (2010). Vrednost brenda za potrošače i preduzeća. *Marketing*, 41(1), 3-16.
- Wantah, A. M., & Mandagi, D. W. (2024). Social Media Marketing and Fast-Food Restaurant Brand Loyalty: The Mediating Role of Brand Gestalt. *Jurnal Informatika Ekonomi Bisnis*, 337-343.
- Waworuntu, E. C., Mandagi, D. W., & Pangemanan, A. S. (2022). I see it, I want it, I buy it: The role of Social media marketing in Shaping the brand image and Gen Z's Intention to purchase local products. *Society*, 10(2), 351-369.
- Wielki, J. (2020). Analysis of the role of digital influencers and their impact on the functioning of the contemporary online promotional system and its sustainable development. *Sustainability*, 12(17), 7138.

- Wiweka, K., Wahyuni, N., Teviningrum, S., & Suheryadi, H. (2023). The influence of YouTube food content reviews on customer purchasing decisions: a lesson from Jakarta local street food. *International Journal of Applied Sciences in Tourism and Events*, 7(2), 147-156.
www.statista.com/statistics/1446950/gen-z-internet-users-social-media-use/,
 retrieved: 25.07.2024.
- Yang, F. X. (2017). Effects of restaurant satisfaction and knowledge sharing motivation on eWOM intentions: the moderating role of technology acceptance factors. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 41(1), 93-127.
- Yarış, A., & Aykol, Ş. (2022). The impact of social media use on restaurant choice. *Anatolia*, 33(3), 310-322.
- Zhang, Z., Ye, Q., Law, R., & Li, Y. (2010). The impact of e-word-of-mouth on the online popularity of restaurants: A comparison of consumer reviews and editor reviews. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 29(4), 694-700.

Questionnaire

U1	I use social media to find information about restaurants.
U2	Restaurant reviews on social media help me decide to visit a restaurant.
U3	Social media ratings are important to me when choosing a restaurant.
U4	I value the ratings of real restaurant guests, more than the ratings on social networks.
U5	To make sure that the restaurant is good, I often read the reviews of the restaurant's guests.
U6	I don't read the reviews and recommendations of other guests when choosing a restaurant.
SM1	Facebook
SM2	Instagram
SM3	TikTok
SM4	X-Twitter
SM5	YouTube
I1	The way the influencers present the restaurant is important to me.
I2	The exciting approach of presenting food in a restaurant by influencers is important to me.
I3	The presentation of food by influencers stimulates my appetite.
I4	Representation of the ambiance of the restaurant by the influencer is important to me.

I5	I always look for restaurant reviews from influencers.
I6	An influencer's rating will make me want to visit the restaurant.
I7	An influencer's recommendation encourages me to visit a restaurant.